

Observations on the running spider *Suemus punctatus* Lawrence, 1938 from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Suemus punctatus* Lawrence, 1938, is known from Eswatini, Mozambique, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. They are free-living plant dwellers found on grasses and occasionally on shrubs. Their movements are erratic, and using their claw tufts and scopulae, they can move about swiftly on the vegetation. Information on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution in South Africa, with photographs of live specimens, is provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation biography, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

One of the little-known philodromid genera is *Suemus* Simon, 1895. Five species of *Suemus* are known, of which three are based on juvenile specimens including the type species *Suemus atomarius* described from Sierra Leone. Two species have been recorded from Vietnam and three from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Only *Suemus punctatus* Lawrence, 1938, known from both sexes, is known from Southern Africa.

Many Philodromidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), and some specimens were identified as *S. punctatus*.

Here, *S. punctatus* is discussed, and more information is provided on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution. Some colour variations are discussed based on photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled ($n=35$) collected during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. SANSa requested photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several photographs of the species were received from the public.

TAXONOMY

Suemus punctatus Lawrence, 1938

Suemus punctatus Lawrence, 1938: 490 (m); Lawrence, 1942: 166 (f); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 24, p. 23 (mf).

Diagnostic characteristics: *Female.* Size: TL females 6–7mm. Body cryptic; carapace creamish brown, with broad paler median band; bordered by two broad darker bands from posterior eyes to posterior edge; margin with narrow pale margin broadening towards posterior edge (Fig. 1). Carapace slightly flattened, as wide as long; sub-oval in outline; thoracic region evenly rounded (Fig. 2), sloping gently posteriorly; fovea not very distinct; with spotted appearance seen in alcohol material (Fig 5 & 6). Eyes: 8 in 2 rows (4:4) (Fig. 5); both rows recurved; posterior row more strongly; median ocular quadrangle wider than long, narrower anteriorly; eyes small same size (Fig. 4). Abdomen oval; covered with dense pale setae layer (Figs 1 & 5); dorsum decorated with five small dark spots (Figs 1, 5 & 6). Legs the same colour as carapace; decorated with numerous dark spots; slender, arranged sideways, legs II slightly longer than rest. Epigyne shows several degrees of variation (Figs 9 & 10). *Male.* Total length 4–5 mm. Male bright orange-yellow, decorated with numerous dark setae and spots (Figs 4 & 7). Carapace flattened, a little longer than wide. Abdomen variable with or without black spots. Legs long and slender; spotted; distal leg segments dark (Figs 3 & 13). Male palp (Figs 9 & 12).

Figures 1–4. *Suemus punctatus* 1. Female, dorsal view. 2. Female, anterior view. 3. Male dorsal view from Ukuwela NR. 4. Male eye pattern, anterior view. Photos: 1–4. Ruan Booysen.

Figures 5–8. *Suemus punctatus*. 5 & 6. Female dorsal view, in alcohol. 7. Male dorsal view, in alcohol. 8. Drawing of abdomen. Credits: 5-7. ASD. 8. After Lawrence, 1938.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Eswatini, Mozambique, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 14). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorst-spruit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Hammanskraal (-25.41, 28.27). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37; 32.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.94, 32.47); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park: Shingwedzi (20km SE) (-22.93, 31.02); Pafuri (-22.46, 31.3); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); University of Limpopo, Sovenga Hill, (-24.17, 29); Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.9, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25, 31.97); Kruger National Park, Mopani, Tsendze (-23.691, 31.518); Lapalala Wilderness Game Reserve (-23.84, 28.26); Graskop, 30 km N (-24.93, 30.84); Kruger National Park Lwakahle 08 (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park, Vutomi 09 (-24.61, 31.79). **Northern Cape:** Eselsfontein Farm, S of Grootdrink (-28.62, 21.68); Hopetown (Suffolk Farm) (-29.58, 24.24). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Gouritsmond (Borrelfontein) (-34.34, 21.87); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.61, 19.34); Robben Island (-33.8076, 18.3712); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21).

Figures 9–13. *Suemus punctatus*. 9 & 10. Epigyne. 11 & 12. Male palp. 13. Male from Hammanskraal. Credits: 9 After Lawrence (1938). 11. After Lawrence (1942). 10 & 12. ASD. 13. Vida van der Walt.

Figure 14. Known distribution of *Suemus punctatus*. Credit: S. Foord.

LIFESTYLE

Suemus punctatus are small running spiders frequently encountered on vegetation. Their movements are erratic but swift, and their claw tufts and scopulae enable speedy movement. Their laterigrade legs and flat bodies also allow them to hide in crevices. The egg sacs are usually deposited on leaves.

They were sampled with sweeping and beating vegetation but were also sampled with pitfall traps from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

Protected in several protected areas such as Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

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